

Entrepreneurship and Ethics – Perspective of Gen Z

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Abstract

It has been explored by several researchers that the pattern of development of entrepreneurship among different generation depends upon several aspects of economy. It is also highlighted that generation Z has no desire to be controlled by any other person or boss. By being an entrepreneur, generation Z can actually contribute to the cause they believe in and also be a significant factor of the global economy. This generation openly demonstrates their concern for ethics of certain practices within the tech world. Their experience with the pandemic, natural response to the lock downs, quarantine and school/business closure, high unemployment rate has developed a collective consciousness for generation Z and molded their world view towards ethics and entrepreneurship. The paper attempts to study the relationship between the entrepreneurial intent of generation Z with reference to their characteristics and the role played by ethical values in current scenario.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Generation Z, Entrepreneurial Spirit, Ethics, Entrepreneurial Intent

Introduction

Worldwide there is an on-going dialogue about doing businesses ethically. It is often argued that it is difficult for business to be both ethical and profitable. However, over the years with entrepreneurship gaining importance (Peters et al., 2014) and studies focusing on need of ethics in the way businesses run, the discussion around this topic has gained more significance. The idea that business has obligations towards the society where it operates, has forced researchers and policy makers to dig deep in to this issue.

Entrepreneurship globally is accepted as growth engine for any economy. The need for entrepreneurial activities for developing countries is also emphasized at all platforms by head of states of these countries from time to time (Reynold et al, 2005). It is also observed that innovative measures are adopted by these economies to inculcate the culture of entrepreneurship at grass root level (Davey et al, 2011). The growth of startup culture in such economies provide the right kind of push for the growth of economic activities which cannot be ignored (Peters et al, 2014). The skills and capabilities developed through entrepreneurial culture bring benefits at all level of society (Davey et al, 2011).

It has been explored by several researchers that the pattern of development of entrepreneurship among different generation depends upon several aspects of economy. These aspects vary from social fabric to technological progress, and from government policies to environmental changes in addition to individual traits of personality (Cooper & Dunkelberg, 1986; Schollhammer, 1982; Webster, 1977, Lumpkin and Dess, 1996). Moreover, the expectations of the latest generation to enter the workforce, (Gen Z) needs to carefully analyzed to understand their way of conducting business. Also, in current times, businesses are expected to act as responsible stewards contributing to the growth and success of both their companies and their communities (Abramov and Johnson, 2003). The present study makes an attempt to understand the view of the potential entrepreneurs on ethics.

Generation Z and Entrepreneurial Intent

According to a survey, Generation Z are the largest generation ever and comprise of almost 30% of the world's population (Mccrindle, 2019). Generation Z, in Singh (2017) framework, is the group of people born after 1990. Flippin (2017) defines generation Z as those born after 1995. In both frameworks, generation Z is referred to as the following generation to follow generations X and Y (latter referred to as millennials). Their study highlights that how this generation is motivated by passion, flexibility, autonomy and trust more than monetary incentives (Erkut, 2021). The young businesspeople of today who are part of the entrepreneurial culture are actually part of Generation Z. Generation Z is viewed as ethnically diverse and technologically sophisticated. They have an individual, informal and straight forward in their communication and social networking plays a vital role in their lives (Singh & Dangmei, 2017). Therefore, it becomes imperative for industry and academia to understand how that entrepreneurial mindset can be cultivated in generation Z and used in the ethical way to contribute to the development of economy.

Currently, generation Z drives attention of scholars, but empirical evidence about their aspirations, perspectives, and motivations is either very general, mixed or – when it comes to ethical entrepreneurial mindset – very limited studies are conducted. Some of the characteristics of generation Z for example higher need for achievement, constant appetite to perform better and efforts to get more and more in short duration consequently play a pivot role in their desire to be an entrepreneur (Farrukh, 2018, Chen et al., 2012).

Purnomo et al. (2019) in their research asserted that 50 percent of generation Z is keen to take up entrepreneurship as their career choice. It is also highlighted that generation Z has no desire to be controlled by any other person or boss. They have high self-confidence and believe that they can bring change to the world with their actions (Farrukh, 2018). Unlike Generation Y, that witnessed a lot of material comfort and a consumer driven economy, members of Generation Z has seen more challenging times. They've seen their parents struggle and most recently world engulfed in Covid 19 pandemic, which could explain the emphasis on job creation (Middlemiss, 2015; Parker & Igielnik, 2020). By being an entrepreneur, generation Z can actually contribute to the cause they believe in and also be a significant factor of the global economy (Irawanto&Novianti, 2021).

In an article for Forbes, Schroeder (2020) highlights how studies assert that more than 50% of members of Gen Z are interested in becoming entrepreneurs. On similar lines a survey was conducted by Gallup where they surveyed students and findings suggest that 40 percent of

grades five to 12 students want to become entrepreneurs. This tech savvy generation get mentorship in unconventional ways. They have multiple mentors from various social media communities (Samuelson, C., 2020). A debt-free and purposeful life along with being sensitive to the concerns of the planet are found to drive the entrepreneurial ambitions of this generation (Schroeder, 2020).

Generation Z and Ethical Values

The complex world of business runs on the dynamics of profit, scarcity of resources, fairness, and equality. The ethical decision making process under pressure situations- like resource crunch and ambiguous environment- is largely affected in case of new ventures or startups (Boyd and Gumpert, 1983, Chau and Siu, 2000). The strained decisions of entrepreneurs due to alteration in standard practices out of resource crunch or ambiguity affect interest of all stakeholders (De Clercq and Dakhli, 2009).

Previous researchers have pointed out that in the global economy, ethics are important not only for large firms but also for small scale or startups, the organizations where generations Z is at the helm of affairs (Bucar and Hisrich, 2001, Spence and Rutherford, 2003). Some of the major concerns raised in such situation as highlighted by (Dees and Starr, 1992) are division of profits within the organization, high risk associated with newness, and the tradeoff between impression management, legitimation, and honesty. Generation Z in entrepreneurial role also face these ethical dilemmas while starting up a new venture. In the current scenario business decisions are also affected by outbreak of COVID 19 and changed economic conditions because of that. Attias-Donfut (1988) in his study defined generations as the group or individuals who are born around same time period and have gone through same life altering events such as war, revolutions or diseases. They experienced the similar kind of dilemmas while dealing with these common problems which in Gentina, (2020) has termed as shared history and experience for Generation Z.

Stahl (2021) in her article for Forbes has elaborated on how Gen Z members are different from their predecessors. Based on her personal experience of working with members of different generations, she shares how working with Gen Z clients, who are new entrants to the workforce was different. The author points out that members of Gen Z have very values-driven approach to their careers and job prospects. This generation openly demonstrates their concern for ethics of certain practices within the tech world. Their experience with the pandemic, natural response to the lock downs, quarantine and school/business closure, high unemployment rate has developed a collective consciousness for generation Z and molded their world view towards ethics and entrepreneurship.

Generation Z members are found to actively seek for organizations that exhibit genuine ties with community and social responsibility. They want to see companies creating jobs within their community. Unlike Generation Y, that witnessed a lot of material comfort and a consumer driven economy, members of Generation Z has seen more challenging times. They've seen their parents struggle and most recently world engulfed in Covid 19 pandemic, which could explain the emphasis on job creation (Middlemiss, 2015; Parker & Igielnik, 2020).

Broadbent et al. (2017) in their research work have highlighted that values of generation Z are influenced traditionally by their parents first (89%) followed by friends (78%), teachers

(70%), and then celebrities (30%) and politicians (17%). The ongoing uncertainties of the business environment are a trigger for generation Z to believe less in seeking secured jobs rather they are putting more weightage to risk taking and entrepreneurial capabilities. This is supported by the research work asserting 72% of high school students and 65% of college students want to start their own business (Gentina&Delécluse, 2018).

Across the globe, organizations are designing their own code of conduct to address the emerging and prevalent issues related to ethics. The challenge is more for small and medium size enterprises as they are faced with the constant pressure to sustain in the competitive market. The Deloitte Global (2021) Millennial and Gen Z survey also indicates that more than half of the Gen Z respondents believe in their individual power to drive change. Also, Francis and Hoefel (2018) in their study for Mckinsey and Company highlight that members of Gen Z look for seeking truth. Unlike previous generations, members of Gen Z are more idealistic, confrontational and less willing to accept diverse points of view. Hence, it may be inferred that these future entrepreneurs are most likely to be ethical in their way of doing business.

Entrepreneurial Spirit and Generation Z

The success story of young entrepreneurs has inspired growing pool of members of generation Z. The growing support from the existing ecosystem has further helped members of this generation achieve their desire to work at their own pace as they seek to find solutions to the existing problems of the society.

The theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by Ajzen (1991) which is a popular framework to measure Entrepreneurial Intention, explains that intentional behavior must consider personal and social factors, and a more positive attitude will make the intention more viable to be carried out (Liñán, et al., 2010). Most of previous studies conducted on Entrepreneurial intention focused mainly on the family background (Ranwala, 2016; Farrukh, et al., 2017). However, Kusumawardani and Richard (2020) who studied entrepreneurship intention among Chinese Indonesian Gen Z, talked about how entrepreneurial self-efficacy influences entrepreneurial intention.

Self-efficacy may be defined a faith in one's capacity to be able to create a business activity based on personal assessment of entrepreneurial skills (Dempsey and Jennings, 2014). Further, leadership, experiences at workplace, role models, and emotional arousal might also become some factors affecting self-efficacy (Santoso, 2016). Over the recent years, studies have suggested that individual's belief in their capabilities influences their intention to become an entrepreneur and start a new business (Kusumawardani and Richard, 2020; Farrukh et al., 2017).

Research Methods

In this study, 303 responses were collected through structured questionnaire via online gateway using Google forms through non probability random sampling method. The study was conducted by applying a 5 item scale adapted from (J. Cronin Jr., 1992). These scales were anchored by 'Strongly disagree' coded as 1 and 'Strongly agree' coded as 5 and they were measured on a 5-point Likert-type scale.

Reliability of scale

Reliability of the above mentioned scales was checked by computing cronbach alpha, a measure of reliability which found to be satisfactory. All the variables' coefficient of alpha was above 0.6 specifying a satisfactory internal consistency (Nunnally, 1978).

Hypothesis of the study

1. H0: There is no positive influence of Gen Z characteristics on ethical values leading to Entrepreneurial Intent.
2. H0: There is no positive influence of Gen Z characteristics on Entrepreneurial Spirit leading to Entrepreneurial Intent.
3. H0: There is no positive influence of Entrepreneurial Spirit on ethical values leading to Entrepreneurial Intent.
4. H0: There is no positive influence of Entrepreneurial Essence on Entrepreneurial Intent.

Data Analysis

For data analysis we ran the data through AMOS 18.0 and did two stage procedures to execute SEM analysis through AMOS. In the first step we tried to found out the quality and adequacy of measurement scales through CFA by taking into consideration reliability, convergent and divergent validity, after which we performed second step in which we tested causal relationships among latent variable. In each step, MLE (Maximum Likelihood estimation) method was applied (Byrne, 2001). To assess the GOF (Goodness-of-fit), multiple indicators namely χ^2 (chi-square), χ^2/df (chi-square to degree of freedom ratio), CFI(comparative fit index),GFI (goodness-of-fit index),TLI (Tucker–Lewis index),and RMSEA(root mean square error of approximation) were considered. According to (Hair et al.,1998) model fit is good when indices $Z > 0.90$, χ^2 / df is between 2 and 5, and RMSEA is > 0.08 .

Figure 1 Framework proposed by Authors

Framework proposed by authors

Figure 2 SEM Network

Interpretation

Validity of Measurement Model

To test the measurement model, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was performed using maximum likelihood estimation (MLE). All GOF statistics were falling within acceptable limit ($\chi^2= 268.429$, $df= 125$, $P= 0.000$, $GFI=.930$; $TLI=.927$; $CFI=.940$; $RMSEA=.062$). On the basis of (Jöreskog and Sörbom's 1993) recommendations, it was found out that all items were significant ($t > 2.58$) with factor loading ($\lambda > 0.5$) except one item EV 2 ($\lambda = 0.43$). This item was deleted and CFA was run again resulting into excellent model fit ($\chi^2= 268.429$, $df= 125$, $P= 0.000$, $GFI=.930$; $TLI=.927$; $CFI=.940$; $RMSEA=.062$). Moreover we checked the uni- dimensionality of all constructs through CFI (standard > 0.9 ; Kline, 1998) and standardized root mean square residual (SRMR < 0.08 ; Hu and Bentler, 1998), based on this all the constructs were uni-dimensional (CFI=.940; RMSEA=.062). Then construct validity was checked through establishing convergent validity and discriminant validity (Hair et al., 1998).

For convergent validity two approaches were used (i) factors which were significant with a factor loading above 0.5 and (ii) all AVE values were very close to 0.5 (Fornell and Larcker, 1981), and composite reliabilities were above 0.7 (Hair et al., 1998). Based on this we can say that strong convergent validity was proved (Refer Table No-3). Moreover we applied Fornell and Larcker's (1981) methodology for discriminant validity by comparing square root of AVE with squared correlations between constructs. Table 4 showed discriminant validity as square root of AVE exceeds the squared correlations

Table 1 Reliability Analysis

	Item	Cronbach's alpha	Factor loading	AVE	Composite Reliability
Gen Z Characters	Gen Z 1	0.751	0.671	0.38	0.76
	Gen Z 2		0.589		
	Gen Z 3		0.536		
	Gen Z 4		0.722		
	Gen Z 5		0.563		
Ethical Value	EV 1	0.757	0.611	0.43	0.75
	EV 3		0.566		
	EV 4		0.724		
	EV 5		0.717		
Entrepreneurial Spirit	ES1	0.814	0.683	0.57	0.84
Essence of Entrepreneur	EE1	0.844	0.833	0.73	0.85
	EE2		0.88		

Variable	Number of statements	Cronbach alpha
Gen Z Characters	5 items	.751
Ethical Value	4 items	.748*
Entrepreneurial Spirit	4 items	.814
Essence of Entrepreneur	2 items	.844

Table 2 Discriminant validity

	GEN Z	EV	ES	EE
GEN Z	0.62			
EV	0.02	0.66		
ES	0.41	0.30	0.76	
EE	0.01	0.28	0.37	0.86

Table 3 Convergent Validity**Test of Structural Model**

After confirming the measurement model through CFA, we carried out SEM. The results were acceptable fit to the data ($\chi^2= 303.015$, $df= 130$, $P= 0.000$, $GFI=.925$; $TLI=.915$; $CFI=.928$; $RMSEA=.066$) with a better explanatory power ($R^2= 0.36$).

Standardized coefficients estimates pointed that path between EV and Gen Z characteristics ($\beta= 0.72$; $t=8.9$, $p< 0.05$), between Entrepreneurial Spirit and Entrepreneurial Essence ($\beta= 0.76$; $t=11.604$, $p< 0.05$) and EE and Entrepreneurial Intent ($\beta= 0.60$; $t=9.673$, $p< 0.05$) were significant and positive. While the path for Gen Z characteristics and Entrepreneurial Essence was non-significant ($\beta= -0.04$; $t=-0.645$, $p> 0.05$) (Table 4)

Table: 4- Path Analysis

Paths	Coefficients(beta)	t- Value	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect	Hypothesis Supported
GEN Z →	-0.04	-0.645	-0.04	-	-0.04	No
EV →	0.72	8.9	0.72	-	0.72	Yes
ES →	0.76	11.604	0.76	-	0.76	Yes
EE →	0.60	9.673	0.60	-	0.60	Yes

Findings

The overall finding is divided into two parts; first part is related to impact of Entrepreneurial Spirit and Ethics while the second part is related to impact of various demographic factors on Characteristics.

- Gen Z Characteristics such as Preference to Transparency and personal freedom, Preference to work environment which is friendly and allows for flexible schedules, Preference to Organization that values Diversity, Search for socially responsible Organizations is having significant and positive relation with Ethical Value. So respondent will be more positive towards entrepreneurship if they have some entrepreneurial characters
- Entrepreneurial Intent is positively impacted by characteristics of generation Z and

entrepreneurial spirit. The Entrepreneurial intent is moderated by entrepreneurial essence/self-efficacy of Generation Z members, influenced by ethical values.

Therefore we may infer that characteristics of generation Z leads to enhanced entrepreneurial intent. It may also be added that ethical values stimulate the adoption of entrepreneurship in generation Z as a career choice.

Demographic factors impact on adoption

- The gender has no impact on entrepreneurial spirit of generation Z among the defined characteristics.
- EE with regard to Gen Z characteristics, signifying that education has negligible impact on ES.
- EE & ES among males and females signifies that Gen Z characteristics impact the Entrepreneurial Intent. If we compare both males and females, the Entrepreneurial Intent of Entrepreneurship is higher among the males.
- It is also noted that age of customer does not impact the Entrepreneurial Intent.
- Moreover it was found out that income does impact the Entrepreneurial Intent. As the income increases the intent increases, generation Z respondent having income greater than 10,000 per month adopts Entrepreneurship easily in comparison to those having income of less than 10,000 p.m.

Discussion and Way forward

Based on the in-depth analysis of the collected data and detailed review of previous literature, the framework proposed by authors clearly suggests that Gen Z members have Entrepreneurial intention. The same aptly finds support from literature reviewed in the present paper which suggests that that majority of high school students and college students want to start their own business (Gentina&Delécluse, 2018). Also, characteristics of Gen Z members and their belief in their capabilities (Self efficacy) was found to impact their intention to become an entrepreneur. This again, is supported by previous studies asserting that members of Gen Z are more idealistic, confrontational and less willing to accept diverse points of view (Kusumawardani and Richard, 2020; Farrukh et al., 2017). It may hence be inferred that being idealistic, they prefer to work in businesses where their personal values are not compromised. These future entrepreneurs are most likely to be ethical in their way of doing business.

Also, it was found that though gender does not impact the entrepreneurial spirit, it has an influence on entrepreneurial Intent. The future studies in this line might further explore why despite the ES, females were found to lack the entrepreneurial Intent.

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